

COMPLEX MEASURES TO FIGHT NEMATODES OF CHICKENS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the complex of strict measures to combat, that is, treatment and prevention of helminthiasis - namtodoses (ascariasis, heterokidosis, capillariosis, syngamosis) common among chickens. These measures are developed based on the results of scientific research and serve as a program for veterinary professionals.

Keywords: helminthosis, nematodosis, spread, seasonal dynamics, deworming, treatment, prevention, chemical prevention, anthelminth, ascaridia, capillaria, heterox.

КОМПЛЕКС МЕР ПО БОРЬБЕ С НЕМАТОДАМИ КУР

Аннотация: В статье приведены сведения о комплексе строгих мер борьбы, то есть лечения и профилактики гельминтозов - намтодозов (аскаридоз, гетерокидоз, капилляриоз, сингамоз), распространенных среди кур. Эти меры разработаны на основе результатов научных исследований и служат программой для ветеринарных специалистов.

Ключевые слова: гельминтозы, нематодозы, распространение, сезонная динамика, дегельминтизация, лечение, профилактика, химическая профилактика, антигельминт, аскаридии, капилляриозы, гетеракс

RELEVANCE OF THE TOPIC

We know that helminths cause serious economic damage to the livestock and poultry industries, and another group of helminths poses a threat to human health. From this point of view, there is no doubt that the correct and complete organization and high-quality implementation of the fight against helminthiasis is an urgent problem.

Today, scientific and practical works are being carried out at the level of state policy in order to develop the poultry sector and provide the population with quality poultry products (eggs, chicken meat). In our research, chicken nematodes (ascaridosis, heterokidosis and capillariosis) have a serious effect on reducing the productivity of chickens and increasing farm output, and the comprehensive organization of treatment and prevention of these helminthosis is an urgent issue.

COMPLEX MEASURES FOR TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF POULTRY NEMATODOSES			
1	Monitoring the spread of nematodes among chickens	1.1. Determination of the spread of nematodes among chickens	
		1.2. Determination of seasonal dynamics of nematodes	
2	Planned (treatment) deworming of chickens	2.1. Establishing a deworming scheme	2.1.1. Determination of the optimal period
			2.1.2. Determination of the amount of deworming
			2.2.1. Individual style

		2.2. Selection of an anthelmintic agent and method of its application	2.2.2. Group method *
3	Pasture (breeding areas) prevention	3.1. Control of nematodes and their reservoir hosts	3.1.1. Elimination of <i>Ascaridia galli</i> **, <i>Heterakis gallinarum</i> **, <i>Capillaria obsignata</i> **, <i>Syngamus</i> nematodes and neutralization of earthworms such as <i>Eisenia foetida</i> and <i>Dendrobaena masiupolinsis</i>
		3.2. Decontamination of sources of infection of chickens with nematodes	3.2.2. Frequent replacement and cleaning of bedding, thermal processing of waste from the poultry house, and then use. Use of artisanal water for irrigation.
4	Chemical prevention against chicken nematodes	4.1. Feed chickens once daily with 0.1% Gossypirin or 0.01% Kufestrol mixed feed until they get rid of nematodes.	

THE MAIN PART

At the first stage of the fight against helminthiasis, monitoring is carried out in the conditions of each region and individual farms, and the composition of helminthiasis, their level of distribution and the dynamics of infection of chickens with helminthiasis according to the seasons of the year are determined. (look at the diagram).

Based on this information, a plan of measures to combat nematodes will be drawn up: the plan will determine the duration of treatment-prophylactic deworming. The optimal duration of deworming is determined taking into account the period of growth of helminthiasis, i.e., the period of increased dynamics.

Another important aspect of the fight against nematodes of chickens is the selection of anthelmintic agents (preparations) used for deworming, in which the species composition of nematodes in each separate area (farm), the level of infection of chickens with nematodes, that is, the extent and intensity of the invasion and taking into account information such as the stage of development of helminths is of particular importance. For example, the main group of helminthiasis of chickens is the use of nematodes - drugs belonging to the group of benzimidazoles (albendazole) and imidazoles (nilverm, levamisole, tetramizole).

The effectiveness of deworming depends on the method of its application. Naturally, deworming animals one by one (individual) gives the highest effect. However, it is convenient and highly effective to use the "group method" when deworming poultry groups. Group deworming is carried out by dissolving anthelmintic agents in the water the animal drinks or mixing it with its feed, or by giving it in the form of special healing-food granules.

In order to prevent the widespread spread of nematodes in chickens, it is necessary to implement nematodes preventive measures, that is, it is necessary to pay attention to the protection of poultry from the external environment - pastures, poultry buildings, inventory and other sources of infestation. Production areas infested with eggs of causative agents of nematodes (ascariasis,

capillariosis, heterokidosis and syngamosis) of chickens, and earthworms such as *Eisenia foetida* and *Dendrobaena masiupolinsis*, which are reservoir hosts of nematodes, and dragonflies feeding on helminths should be consistently implemented. should be increased.

In order to prevent helminthiasis, it is also important to clean the environment from helminth eggs and larvae, to carry out disinfection measures. In this case, it is necessary to change the bedding in the poultry house frequently, to first pass the dung and bedding from the poultry house to heat treatment, and then to use it in the cultivated fields. Also, it is necessary to prevent feeding and entry of wild and transient birds in poultry breeding areas and poultry houses.

CONCLUSION

Another factor to prevent large-scale spread of nematodes among chickens is to stimulate the immunobiological defense of chickens against helminthosis. It is also important to feed chickens with food rich in vitamins, to provide them with enough protein and micro-macroelements. According to the results of the research, it was found that it is very effective to mix stimulants such as gossypirin and kufestrol in the feed of young chicks, and it has very good growth and development and anthelmintic properties of chicks. 2022 - It was confirmed in our experiences in 2023.

In general, in the fight against helminthiasis of chickens, each element of the complex of measures mentioned above should be fully and qualitatively implemented.

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